

THE CORTEX² TEAM

WATCH OUT FOR OUR NEXT OPEN CALL FOR 2023!

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Funded by
the European Union

CORTEX²

REMOTE COLLABORATION MADE EASY WITH XR

We aim to facilitate remote collaboration between workers through next-generation extended reality (XR) technology solutions across a wide range of industries and SMEs.

The highly innovative XR platform we are developing will facilitate work and social activities involving physical interaction with the environment and remote objects — from industrial cooperation to technical training and business meetings.

WHY CORTEX²

Existing services aimed at facilitating remote team collaboration are not yet ready to efficiently and effectively support all types of activities, and XR-based tools, which can enhance remote collaboration and communication, present significant challenges for most businesses.

At CORTEX², we will bridge the divide between widespread video-conferencing tools and XR-based solutions, democratising the uptake of next-generation XR tele-cooperation.

THE CORTEX² RX PLATFORM

To this aim, we are creating an innovative digital workplace using the teleconferencing solution Rainbow, from our partner Alcatel Lucent Enterprise, as a backbone.

THE CORTEX² OPEN CALLS

Once we have progressed with its development, we will look for partners to contribute new modules to improve its functionalities, adaptability and replicability in new domains and use cases.

LET'S CREATE THE NEXT GENERATION OF XR TECHNOLOGIES!

We will invest €4 million in 2 open calls to recruit and support 30 European SMEs and industry actors — from research-oriented institutions to business-driven organisations — in the co-development of our CORTEX² XR platform and its replication in different domains.

STATOR (s3x51n)

2

OPEN CALLS

30

IDEAS

€4

MILLION

WE'RE LOOKING FOR

30

XR INNOVATORS

TECH
STARTUPS
AND SMEs

EUROPEAN
INDUSTRY
PLAYERS

WHAT'S IN IT
FOR YOU?

UP TO €200.000
TO FINANCE YOUR SOLUTION

CONTINUOUS GUIDANCE
AND SUPPORT

Capacity building on CORTEX² and XR technologies & trends,
and access to infrastructure, tools and experts